

Chemical Investigation of the Bark of *Eugenia javanica* Lamk.

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Eugenia javanica, syn. *Syzygium samarangense* (Bl) Merr. and Perry. (Fam. Myrtaceae) is a medium sized shady tree, commonly known in Bengal as "Jamrul". This tree is native of the Andaman and Nicobar Islands, Malacca¹ and now being found in different parts of India. We became interested to undertake a chemical investigation of the plant because of chemotaxonomic interest^{2,3} and since no investigation on it was reported in the literature. The present study reveals the presence of betulinic acid (isolated as its methyl ester), β -sitosterol and a compound m.p. 89.5–90°. The plant material for investigation was collected from the University campus, Golapbag, Burdwan.

The dried and powdered bark (700 g.) of *E. javanica* was extracted with petroleum (60–80°) for 24 hr. The yellowish material (1.5 g.) left after removal of the solvent was separated into ether soluble (0.7 g.) and ether insoluble (0.8 g.) portions. The former fraction was separated into neutral (0.2 g.) and acidic (0.45 g.) fractions by the usual procedure³. The acidic fraction was esterified with diazomethane (prepared from 1 g. nitrosomethylurea). The crude methyl ester on chromatography over a column of deactivated alumina (40 g.) yielded methyl betulinate (0.15 g.), m.p. 219–20°, $[\alpha]_D + 8^\circ$ (CHCl₃), from the petroleum and petroleum-benzene eluates. Its identity has been established from mixed m.p. determination and I.R. spectral comparison with an authentic sample.

The neutral fraction on chromatography over Brockmann alumina (30 g.) provided a substance (0.05 g.), which on crystallisation from ethanol melted at 136.5°. It produced green colouration with Liebermann-Burchard reagent. It was identified as β -sitosterol through mixed m.p. determination, IR spectrum and co-chromatography on a TLC plate with an authentic sample.

The ether insoluble material was crystallised from benzene-ethyl acetate mixture. It had m.p. 89.5–90°. Further work on this material is in progress.

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